

Status-Somber Indices

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 15 June 2022	In this paper, we introduce the status Sombor index, modified status Sombor index and their corresponding exponentials of a graph and compute exact formulas for some standard graphs, wheel graphs and friendship graphs. Also we establish some properties of newly defined status Sombor index.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Let G be a finite, simple, connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_G(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . We refer [1], for other undefined notations and terminologies.

In 1972[2], two degree based topological indices were introduced and studied.

The first and second status indices of a graph G were introduced by Ramane et al. in [3], and they are defined as

$$S_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [\sigma(u) + \sigma(v)],$$

$$S_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sigma_G(u) \sigma_G(v).$$

Recently, some status indices were studied, for example, in [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

The Sombor index was introduced by Gutman in [16] and defined it as

$$SO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2}.$$

Recently, some Sombor indices were studied, for example, in [17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23].

Motivated by the definitions of the status and Sombor indices, we introduce the status-Somber index of a graph and defined it as,

$$SSO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}.$$

We also propose the status Sombor exponential of a graph and it is defined as

$$SSO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}}.$$

We now define the modified status Sombor index of a graph G as

$${}^m SSO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}}.$$

We also propose the modified status Sombor exponential of a graph and it is defined as

$${}^m SSO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}}}.$$

The forgotten topological index of a graph is defined as [24]

$$F(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2).$$

The F-status index of a graph is defined as [25]

$$FS(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2).$$

In this paper, we compute the status Sombor index modified status Sombor index, status Sombor exponential and modified status Sombor exponential of some standard graphs, wheel graphs and friendship graphs. Also we establish some properties of the status Sombor index.

II. RESULTS

2.1. Complete graph K_n on n vertices

Theorem 1. The status Sombor index of a complete graph K_n is

$$SSO(K_n) = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Proof: If K_n is a complete graph with n vertices, then $d_{K_n}(u) = n-1$ and $\square(u) = n-1$ for any vertex u in K_n .

Thus

$$SSO(K_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_n)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \sqrt{(n-1)^2 + (n-1)^2} = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{\sqrt{2}}$$

2.2. Cycle C_n on n vertices

Theorem 2. Let C_n be a cycle on n vertices. Then

$$SSO(C_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n^3}{2\sqrt{2}}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2\sqrt{2}}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Proof: If C_n is a cycle with n vertices, then $d_{C_n}(u) = 2$ for every vertex u in C_n .

Case 1. Suppose n is even. Then $\sigma(u) = \frac{n^2}{4}$ for any vertex u in C_n . Therefore

$$SSO(C_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(C_n)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} = \sum_{uv \in E(C_n)} \sqrt{\left(\frac{n^2}{4}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n^2}{4}\right)^2} = \frac{n^3}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

Case 2. Suppose n is odd. Then $\sigma(u) = \frac{n^2-1}{4}$ for any vertex u in C_n . Thus

$$SSO(C_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(C_n)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} = \sum_{uv \in E(C_n)} \sqrt{\left(\frac{(n-1)^2}{4}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{(n-1)^2}{4}\right)^2} = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

III. RESULTS FOR WHEEL GRAPHS

A wheel W_n is the join of C_n and K_1 . Clearly W_n has $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. A graph W_4 is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Wheel graph W_4

Let W_n be a wheel with $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges.

In W_n , there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d_{W_n}(u) = d_{W_n}(v) = 3\},$$

$$|E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d_{W_n}(u) = 3, d_{W_n}(v) = n\},$$

$$|E_2| = n.$$

Thus there are two types of status edges as given in

Table 1.

Table 1. Status edge partition of W_n

$\sigma(u), \sigma(v) \setminus uv \in E(W_n)$	$(2n-3, 2n-3)$	$(n, 2n-3)$
Number of edges	n	n

Theorem 3. The status Sombor index of a wheel graph W_n is

$$SSO(W_n) = \sqrt{2}n(2n-3) + n\sqrt{5n^2-12n+9}$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 1, we deduce

$$SSO(W_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} = n\sqrt{(2n-3)^2 + (2n-3)^2} + n\sqrt{n^2 + (2n-3)^2} = \sqrt{2}n(2n-3) + n\sqrt{5n^2-12n+9}$$

Theorem 4. The status Sombor exponential of a wheel graph W_n is

$$SSO(W_n, x) = nx^{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)} + nx^{\sqrt{5n^2-12n+9}}$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 1, we have

$$SSO(W_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} x^{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}} = nx^{\sqrt{(2n-3)^2 + (2n-3)^2}} + nx^{\sqrt{n^2 + (2n-3)^2}} = nx^{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)} + nx^{\sqrt{5n^2-12n+9}}$$

Theorem 5. The modified status Sombor index of a wheel graph W_n is

$$SSO(W_n) = \frac{n}{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)} + \frac{n}{\sqrt{5n^2-12n+9}}$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 1, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m SSO(W_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{n}{\sqrt{(2n-3)^2 + (2n-3)^2}} + \frac{n}{\sqrt{n^2 + (2n-3)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{n}{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)} + \frac{n}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 12n + 9}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. The modified status Somber exponential of a wheel graph W_n is

$${}^m SSO(W_n) = nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)}} + nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 12n + 9}}}.$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 1, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m SSO(W_n, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}}} \\
 &= nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{(2n-3)^2 + (2n-3)^2}}} + nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{n^2 + (2n-3)^2}}} \\
 &= nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(2n-3)}} + nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 12n + 9}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

IV. RESULTS FOR FRIENDSHIP GRAPHS

A friendship graph F_n , $n \geq 2$, is a graph that can be constructed by joining n copies of C_3 with a common vertex. A graph F_4 is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Friendship graph F_4

Let F_n be a friendship graph with $2n+1$ vertices and $3n$ edges. By calculation, we obtain that there are two types of edges as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d_{F_n}(u) = d_{F_n}(v) = 2\}, \\
 E_2 &= \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d_{F_n}(u) = 2, d_{F_n}(v) = 2n\},
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, in F_n , there are two types of status edges as given in Table 2.

Table 2. Status edge partition of F_n

$\sigma(u), \sigma(v) \setminus uv \in E(F_n)$	$(4n-2, 4n-2)$	$(2n, 4n-2)$
Number of edges	n	$2n$

In the following theorem, we compute the status Somber index of a friendship graph F_n .

Theorem 7. The status Somber index of a friendship graph F_n is

$$SSO(F_n) = \sqrt{2}n(4n-2) + 4n\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}.$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 2, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 SSO(F_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} \\
 &= n\sqrt{(4n-2)^2 + (4n-2)^2} + 2n\sqrt{(2n)^2 + (4n-2)^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{2}n(4n-2) + 4n\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 8. The status Somber exponential of a friendship graph F_n is

$$SSO(F_n, x) = nx^{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)} + 2nx^{2\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}.$$

Proof: From definition and by using Table 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 SSO(F_n, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} x^{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}} \\
 &= nx^{\sqrt{(4n-2)^2 + (4n-2)^2}} + 2nx^{\sqrt{(2n)^2 + (4n-2)^2}} \\
 &= nx^{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)} + 2nx^{2\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 9. The modified status Somber index of a friendship graph F_n is

$$SSO(F_n) = \frac{n}{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)} + \frac{n}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}.$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 2, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m SSO(F_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{n}{\sqrt{(4n-2)^2 + (4n-2)^2}} + \frac{2n}{\sqrt{(2n)^2 + (4n-2)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{n}{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)} + \frac{n}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 10. The modified status Somber exponential of a friendship graph F_n is

$${}^m SSO(F_n) = nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)}} + 2nx^{\frac{1}{2\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}}.$$

Proof: By using definition and Table 2, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m SSO(F_n, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2}}} \\
 &= nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{(4n-2)^2 + (4n-2)^2}}} + nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{(2n)^2 + (4n-2)^2}}} \\
 &= nx^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(4n-2)}} + 2nx^{\frac{1}{2\sqrt{5n^2 - 4n + 1}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

V. MATHEMATICAL PROPERTIES OF THE STATUS SOMBOR INDEX

Theorem 11. Let G be a connected graph with m edges. Then

$$SSO(G) \leq \sqrt{mFS(G)}.$$

Proof: Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, we obtain

$$\left(\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2} \right)^2 \leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} 1 \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (\sigma(u)^2 + \sigma(v)^2).$$

$$= mFS(G).$$

Thus $SSO(G) \leq \sqrt{mFS(G)}.$

By means of proof techniques analogous to what earlier was used to the Sombor index [26, 27], we establish Theorem 12 and Theorem 13.

Theorem 12. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$SSO(G) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} S_1(G).$$

Equality holds if and only if G is regular.

Theorem 13. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$SSO(G) \leq \sqrt{2}(S_1(G) - S_2(G)).$$

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced the status Sombor index, modified status Sombor index and their exponentials of a graph. These indices and their exponentials of complete graphs, cycles, wheel graphs, friendship graphs have been computed. Also we have established some properties of the status Sombor index.

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